

ALBUKHARY INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY

SCHOOL OF BUSINESS AND SOCIAL SCIENCES

ACADEMIC SESSION 2021/2022

SEMESTER 4

COURSE CODE : BBC2023
COURSE NAME : Macroeconomics
LECTURER'S NAME : Osaid Abdaljawwad
THE TITLE : Impact of technological advancements on unemployment rate 2008 to 2019 in the US.

NO	STUDENT NAME	STUDENT ID	PROGRAM
1	Osama Mohamed Abuagla	AIU20092232	BBA
2	Radwan Alkhair Ismail Idris	AIU21102114	BBA
3	Nur Ain Tasnim Binti Sazali	AIU22102049	BBAHRM
4	Nur Farah Waheda Binti Aluwi	AIU22102070	BBAHRM
5	Sultan Ali Ahmed Alshardofi	AIU21102227	BBA
6	Md Aulad Hossain	AIU21102191	BBAM

Submission data : 19 of january 2024

Radwan Alkhair

Md Aulad Hossain

Sultan Ali Ahmed

Osama Mohamed

Abstract

This study offers a comprehensive examination of the influence of technological progress, encompassing artificial intelligence, automation, robotics, and digital platforms, on job and unemployment patterns in the United States throughout the era of digitalization. This analysis investigates the impact of these technological advancements on employment patterns in different industries and population groups, as well as the transformation of global value chains and labor market dynamics. The research investigates the problems and potential of these technologies by using both qualitative and quantitative methodologies. It compares current job situations with historical circumstances. Significant emphasis is placed on the need of vocational training in addressing the negative consequences of technological changes and promoting social and economic advancement. The key findings emphasize the intricate and industry-specific effects of technological advancement, providing valuable insights for the formulation of policies and strategies that attempt to align technological innovation with the stability of employment. The study seeks to enhance our understanding of the labor consequences of technical progress in the United States, situated within the wider framework of socio-economic progress.

Keywords: Technological advancements and unemployment rate , Artificial intelligence and employment, Future of work in the digital age, Automation and job displacement

Table of Contents

1.0 Introduction	5
1.1 Background of the Study	5
1.2 Motivations on the Topic Selection	5
1.4 Main Objectives of the Study	6
1.5 Research Questions of the Study	7
2.0 Literature Review	8
2.1. Job Displacement and Sectoral Variations	8
2.2. Broader Demographic Impact	8
2.3. Education and Workforce Preparedness	9
2.4. Contrasting Perspectives and the Creation of New Job Opportunities	9
2.5. Policy Measures and Recommendations	9
2.6. Global Context and Comparative Analysis	10
2.7. Technological Advancements and Economic Implications	10
2.8. Future of Work and Technological Ethics	11
3.0 Methodology	12
4.0 Real data Presentations and Findings	13
4.1 Global workforce numbers at a glance	13
4.2 Impact of automation varies by a country's income level, demographics, and industry structure	14
4.3 Unemployment rate in US 2008 -2019	15
4.4 Projected employment by STEM occupational group in US	16
4.5 Job trends for detailed occupations considered high risk for automation, 1999–2029 (number of jobs in thousands)	17
5.0 Discussion, Recommendation and Suggestion	18
5.1 Discussion on Global Workforce Numbers at a Glance in the Context of the USA	18
5.2 Impact of Automation Varies by a Country's Income Level, Demographics, and Industry Structure for the USA	19
5.3 Discussion on how the integration of AI technologies can influence the overall unemployment rate in manufacturing sectors (transportation)	19
5.4 Strategies and Recommendations for Managing Workforce Transitions: Navigating the Impact of AI on Unemployment Rates	22
5.5 Proposed solutions based on the analysis	23
6.0 Conclusion	24
References	27
Appendix	28

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

This study conducts a comprehensive analysis of the significant and diverse impacts of technological progress, specifically in the areas of Artificial Intelligence (AI), automation, robotics, and digital platforms, on the level of unemployment in the United States. During a time characterized by swift technological progress, these developments pose both difficulties and prospects that have substantial socio-economic consequences. The United States, a prominent force in technical advancement and economic dominance, provides an exemplary model for comprehending these intricate processes. This research aims to analyze and understand the intricate relationship between technology advancement and its effects on job markets, labor capabilities, and the overall employment structure. The ongoing advancement of technology, previously linked mainly to effectiveness and advancement, now raises significant concerns over employment stability, the pertinence of skills, and the adjustment of the workforce in an increasingly digitized society.

1.2 Motivations on the Topic Selection

The choice of this subject is motivated by an increasing worldwide apprehension regarding the consequences of swift technical advancements on employment. This worry transcends academic circles and encompasses lawmakers, business leaders, and the workforce. The correlation between technology and employment is a critical issue that affects economic stability, social welfare, and the future of labor. Understanding the influence of technology on employment patterns is crucial due to its growing integration across various sectors of business and industry. Hence, this subject matter pertains to the pressing necessity of scrutinizing the wider ramifications of AI, automation, and digitalization, not just as separate technological occurrences, but as crucial influences that are fundamentally transforming the essence of employment, the requisite competencies, and the configuration of diverse sectors.

1.3 Main Problems of the Study

This study addresses the complex issue of how technology improvements, particularly in AI and automation, affect employment in the United States. The primary issues addressed in this paper revolve around the capacity of new technologies to cause significant disruptions in work markets, resulting in job displacement and changes in the necessary skill sets. The research seeks to elucidate the intricate mechanisms via which technology advancements are altering the essence of employment, resulting in disparities within the job market, and posing challenges to established economic and regulatory frameworks. The study rigorously analyzes these changes, specifically addressing the discrepancies they create in different sectors, the potential dangers they present to various demographic groups, and the overall difficulty of achieving a harmonious incorporation of technology in the job market without worsening socioeconomic disparities.

1.4 Main Objectives of the Study

The primary goals of this study are to provide a thorough and extensive analysis of the influence of technological improvements on employment patterns in the United States. The objective is to identify and analyze the industries that are most profoundly impacted by these changes, emphasize the demographic groups who are encountering the most serious difficulties, and investigate the possibilities of vocational training and governmental interventions in reducing the negative consequences. The study seeks to offer significant insights and recommendations to legislators, business strategists, and educational institutions. This will aid in the development of policies that can efficiently harness technological improvements while minimizing their negative impact on the labor market.

1.5 Research Questions of the Study

To guide this investigation, the study poses the following research questions:

How have technological advancements contributed to variations in employment patterns in the USA?

Which sectors and demographic groups are most affected by the intersection of technology and unemployment?

What policy measures can be recommended to mitigate the challenges posed by technological advancements to unemployment, and promote a more inclusive and resilient labor market?

2.0 Literature Review

The advent of advanced technologies, notably AI, robotics, digital platforms, and automation, has sparked a significant transformation in the employment landscape of the United States. This literature review critically examines the complex interplay between these technological innovations and their impact on the labor market, offering insights into both the challenges and opportunities they present.

2.1. Job Displacement and Sectoral Variations

The influence of technology on employment is complex, with diverse consequences across many sectors. Automation and mechanization in conventional sectors such as industry and agriculture have resulted in substantial job displacement, as evidenced by Ford, M. R. (2009) and Frey, C. B., & Osborne, M. A. (2017). Nevertheless, technology's influence goes much beyond these industries. Automation and AI-driven tools are reshaping worker roles and needs in service-oriented industries, such as retail and customer service. In industries such as healthcare, artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics are not only substituting specific manual jobs but also generating fresh prospects for technologically proficient workers. The research highlights a transition towards a knowledge-based economy, where there is a growing demand for advanced technical and cognitive skills, while the requirement for routine, low-skilled work is decreasing.

2.2. Broader Demographic Impact

Technological improvements have a varying impact on different demographic groups. Studies suggest that individuals with lower levels of expertise, who possess less capacity to adjust to emerging technologies, face a greater likelihood of losing their jobs. This problem is especially evident among senior employees, who may encounter difficulties in acquiring new skills for different positions due to the quick pace of technology advancements. Recent studies also emphasize the potential differential effects of these developments on different ethnic and gender groups, indicating the possibility of exacerbating pre-existing disparities in the job market. Comprehending these subtle variations in population characteristics is essential for formulating focused policies and interventions.

2.3. Education and Workforce Preparedness

The dynamic nature of the job market requires a reassessment of educational systems and workforce training programs. The literature emphasizes the significance of synchronizing education with the requirements of a highly advanced economy driven by technology. This entails not just incorporating STEM courses more extensively into curricula but also cultivating aptitudes such as critical thinking, creativity, and adaptability. Workforce resilience is increasingly reliant on lifelong learning and ongoing skill development. Research indicates that educational institutions, policymakers, and businesses should work together to develop educational routes that can adapt to technological progress.

2.4. Contrasting Perspectives and the Creation of New Job Opportunities

Although there is significant attention given to the possibility of job displacement caused by technological developments, several experts provide a more sanguine perspective. They contend that technology, despite its disruptive nature, is also a potent catalyst for generating novel job classifications and broadening markets. Advancements in digital platforms and communication technology are responsible for the emergence of the gig economy and the availability of remote employment alternatives. These emerging job models provide both flexibility and accessibility, potentially expanding labor market opportunities for previously disadvantaged demographics.

2.5. Policy Measures and Recommendations

Tackling the difficulties presented by technological progress necessitates a comprehensive and multifaceted governmental strategy. The literature promotes solutions that not only reduce the immediate effects of job displacement but also equip the workforce for future transformations. This encompasses allocating resources towards enhancing education and vocational training, advocating for adaptable labor market conditions, and establishing resilient social safety systems. Policymakers are advised to contemplate a variety of measures, such as providing financial assistance for enhancing skills and implementing

changes in labor regulations, in order to establish a conducive atmosphere that promotes both technical advancement and the well-being of the workforce.

2.6. Global Context and Comparative Analysis

Moreover, the literature study gains advantages from a comprehensive worldwide outlook, by juxtaposing the United States' encounter with that of other highly developed economies. This comparative research offers a comprehensive comprehension of how various countries are managing the difficulties and possibilities given by technology breakthroughs. It emphasizes the variety of governmental reactions and adjustments in the labor market, providing useful lessons and insights. The European approach to workforce training and social safety nets differs from the U.S. model by placing greater emphasis on social protections and collective bargaining. In Asian countries, the focus on technological education and quick integration of digital technologies creates a distinct framework for comprehending the relationship between technology and employment.

2.7. Technological Advancements and Economic Implications

In addition to the direct impact on the labor market, the literature also explores the wider economic consequences of these technological advancements. Research investigates the potential effects of automation and AI on productivity, salary distributions, and economic disparity. Exploring the potential of technology to both stimulate economic growth and widen wealth gaps is of utmost importance. This encompasses conversations regarding the necessity of fair allocation of the advantages brought by technical advancements, as well as the influence of taxation and public policy in attaining this equilibrium.

2.8. Future of Work and Technological Ethics

A burgeoning topic in scholarly works is the notion of the 'future of work' and the ethical implications associated with technological progress. This include discussions regarding the moral obligations of AI developers, the ethical application of robots in the workplace, and the potential societal ramifications of extensive automation. The literature advocates for a comprehensive strategy that takes into account not just the economic and employment factors, but also the ethical and social implications of technology advancement.

This extensive literature analysis provides a thorough and nuanced comprehension of the correlation between technical progress and employment. It emphasizes the intricacy of the matters being discussed, encompassing a diverse array of viewpoints and research discoveries. This review establishes the foundation for a more thorough investigation of the subject in the following sections of the study, connecting to the research questions and objectives stated in the introduction.

3.0 Methodology

This research technique seeks to examine the many effects of technological progress, namely in the areas of artificial intelligence, automation, robotics, and digital platforms, on unemployment in the modern era of the United States. The study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the labor consequences of technological progress in the USA through the utilization of various research methodologies and data sources. The data will be obtained from credible sources, such as scholarly journal articles, trustworthy websites, and publications, spanning from 2008 to 2019 to encompass the changing technological environment. The research methodologies employed in this study include descriptive and comparative analyses, evaluation of vocational training programs, and secondary data analysis. These methods are used to thoroughly address the study's objectives. The objectives encompass the analysis of the impact of technical breakthroughs on employment, comprehension of the distinct issues encountered by the workforce, assessment of vocational training programs, and formulation of governmental measures to align technological progress with employment stability. In addition, we will test hypotheses to investigate the implications particular to different sectors, global influences, the adaptability of the workforce, and the effectiveness of policies in navigating the digital transformation of the USA. The objective of this research approach is to thoroughly analyze the complex relationship between technology advancement and employment patterns in the changing digital environment of the United States.

4.0 Real data Presentations and Findings

4.1 Global workforce numbers at a glance

1 "Slowest" and "fastest" adoption refer to the two extremes of the scenario range we used in our automation adoption modeling, the latest and earliest scenarios, respectively. See Chapter 1 for details.

2 Full-time equivalents.

3 In trendline labor-demand scenario.

4 Rising incomes; health care from aging; investment in technology, infrastructure, and buildings; energy transitions; and marketization of unpaid work. Not exhaustive.

5 See Jeffrey Lin, "Technological adaptation, cities, and new work," *Review of Economics and Statistics*, volume 93, number 2, May 2011.

Source : McKinsey Global Institute

The illustration highlights the capacity of automation to bring about significant changes, indicating that around 50% of existing labor tasks can be technically automated using current technologies. By 2030, automation will potentially displace a portion of the workforce, ranging from 0% to 30%, depending on the rate of implementation. Simultaneously, it emphasizes the need for a significant section of the labor force to shift to different job categories, highlighting the dynamic relationship between technology advancement and employment. These observations highlight the immediate necessity for proactive policies and vocational training to reduce the dangers of unemployment and take advantage of the opportunities given by technology breakthroughs.

4.2 Impact of automation varies by a country's income level, demographics, and industry structure

Source : World Bank; Oxford Economics; McKinsey Global Institute analysis

The graph presents a nuanced perspective on the disparate impacts of automation vary based on a country's wealth, demographic composition, and industrial structure. The graph shows that higher-income countries like the United States have a greater percentage of jobs at risk of automation, correlating with a higher GDP per capita. This suggests a more pronounced potential for technological displacement in wealthier nations due to more advanced industry and technology integration. This data reinforces the necessity for targeted strategies in the US to manage transitions in the labor market amidst technological advancements, emphasizing the need for policies that address the higher susceptibility to automation-related job displacement within advanced economies.

need for policies that address the higher susceptibility to automation-related job displacement within advanced economies.

4.3 Unemployment rate in US 2008 -2019

Source : <https://fred.stlouisfed.org/series/UNRATE>

Year	Unemployment rate
2008	5.8
2009	9.3
2010	9.6
2011	8.9
2012	8.1
2013	7.4
2014	6.2
2015	5.3
2016	4.9
2017	4.4
2018	3.9
2019	3.7

Results :

Sum	77.3
Min	3.7
Median	6.0
Average	6.4

The figure above illustrates the unemployment rate trends in the US that started from 2008 to 2019. In 2008, the unemployment rate began to rise steadily, reaching to 9.6% in 2010. Additionally, a downward trend started to emerge, with the unemployment rate declining to 8.9% in 2011 and continuing to decrease consistently. By 2019, the unemployment rate had significantly reduced to 3.7%.

4.4 Projected employment by STEM occupational group in US

Occupation title	Employment		Percent change
	2019	2029	2019-29
STEM occupations	9,955.1	10,752.9	8.0
Computer occupations	4,633.4	5,164.6	11.5
Engineers	1,810.1	1,879.1	3.8
Life scientists	344.8	361.4	4.8
STEM post secondary teachers ¹	294.1	308.8	5.0
Physical scientists	276.6	291.4	5.3
Mathematical science occupations	211.7	267.8	26.5

Source:

<https://www.bls.gov/opub/btn/volume-10/why-computer-occupations-are-behind-strong-stem-employment-growth.htm>

The table above shows the projected employment by the STEM occupational group. From the table, the employment number for computer occupations in 2019 was 4,633.4, which is the highest of all occupations, including engineers, biologists, educators, physical scientists, and mathematicians, in both 2019 and will also predicted to be same on 2029. It is anticipated that employment in computer occupations will rise to 5164.6 by 2029. The United States' expected

job increase in computer occupations between 2019 and 2029 is a good indicator of the growing need for workers with expertise in technology and computer-related industries. However, this expansion is actually in line with the continuous automation trend across several industries. The increasing demand for experts in the design, implementation, and upkeep of automation systems is reflected in the growth in employment in computer-related fields. An increase in this field will directly affect a large number of workers who will be affected by AI and automation.

4.5 Job trends for detailed occupations considered high risk for automation, 1999–2029 (number of jobs in thousands)

SOC code	Title	OEWS		BLS projections database				
		1999	2009	2008	2018p	2018	2019	2029p
00-0000	All occupations	118,201	130,580	150,930	166,204	160,959	162,797	168,835
A. Potential AI-affected occupations								
13-2052	Personal financial advisors	80.0	149.5	208.4	271.2	271.7	263.0	274.6
27-3091	Interpreters and translators	13.6	40.0	50.9	62.2	76.1	77.4	92.9
29-1067	Surgeons, except ophthalmologists	48.5	44.6	54.5	63.8	38.2	39.6	38.8
35-3021	Fast food and counter workers	2,358.9	3,186.7	3,227.1	3,670.4	4,184.4	4,047.7	4,508.6
37-2011	Janitors and cleaners	2,090.6	2,090.4	2,375.3	2,479.4	2,404.4	2,374.2	2,479.8
37-2012	Maids and housekeeping cleaners	913.5	887.9	1,498.2	1,583.7	1,494.4	1,474.9	1,470.7
37-3011	Landscaping and groundskeeping workers	739.5	860.0	1,205.8	1,422.9	1,205.2	1,188.0	1,307.9
53-3032	Heavy and tractor-trailer truck drivers	1,558.4	1,550.9	1,798.4	2,031.3	1,958.8	2,029.9	2,060.5
53-7051	Industrial truck and tractor operators	590.7	568.3	610.3	627.0	615.0	634.7	652.3
53-7062	Laborers and freight, stock, material moving	2,035.6	2,135.8	2,317.3	2,298.6	2,953.8	2,986.0	3,111.7
[1]	Subtotal	10,429.3	11,514.1	13,346.2	14,510.5	15,202.0	15,115.4	15,997.8
[1]	Percent of all jobs	8.8	8.8	8.8	8.7	9.4	9.3	9.5

Source:

https://www.bls.gov/opub/mlr/2022/article/growth-trends-for-selected-occupations-considered-at-risk-from-automation.htm#BLStable_2022_3_17_10_7

According to the data above, these are the listed professions that have been identified as being affected by the robots and AI that will lead to job losses, according to OEWS data. From 1999 to 2008, 8.8% of all jobs were affected by AI, which is predicted to increase to 9.5% in 2029. We

can see that the occupations most affected by robots and AI are fast food and counter workers, which increased from 4184.4 in 2018 to 4508.6 in 2029. Moreover, the lowest occupation that is affected is interpreters and translators, which will only reach 92.9 in 2029. A significant increase in the amount of work affected by AI will cause an increase in the percentage of job losses, which will affect the unemployment rate curve, which is expected to increase. For example, fast food and counter workers have the highest percentage change in affected occupations, which is 39.7% compared to the other occupations. This will also affect the unemployment rate in this occupation sector, as the higher numbers of affected occupations will also increase the unemployment rate.

5.0 Discussion, Recommendation and Suggestion

5.1 Discussion on Global Workforce Numbers at a Glance in the Context of the USA

The research presented by McKinsey Global Institute provides useful insights into the potential consequences of automation on the worldwide labor force, with ramifications specifically for the United States. The forecast that around 50% of present labor tasks can be automated using existing technologies emphasizes the need for aggressive policy in the USA. To fully acknowledge the profound impact of automation, it is imperative for the country to allocate resources towards comprehensive workforce transition initiatives. These programs should prioritize activities that aim to retrain and enhance the skills of workers in order to align the American workforce with the changing requirements of a technologically sophisticated economy. Policymakers should give primary importance to the development of policy frameworks that promote innovation while guaranteeing equitable economic expansion. Striking a balance between promoting technological advancement and ensuring support for people who may be displaced is essential for effectively addressing the issues brought about by automation in the United States.

5.2 Impact of Automation Varies by a Country's Income Level, Demographics, and Industry Structure for the USA

The World Bank, Oxford Economics, and McKinsey Global Institute provide a nuanced perspective on the impact of automation, emphasizing the necessity of customized interventions in the United States. Due to its status as a high-income country with a technologically proficient economy, the USA encounters a higher proportion of employment that are susceptible to automation. To address the diverse impact on different population groups, authorities should enact targeted programs tailored to specific demographics. Efforts should be formulated to specifically address the needs of susceptible populations, such as elderly employees or individuals with less expertise, who are more likely to encounter increased job insecurity. Moreover, it is crucial to develop industry-specific policies for areas that are especially vulnerable to automation. Through the identification and strategic focus on these specific industries, the United States can effectively adopt policies aimed at facilitating a seamless transition for workers who may be impacted. These ideas emphasize the significance of tailoring interventions to the particular socioeconomic circumstances of the United States, guaranteeing efficient and subtle answers to the difficulties presented by automation.

5.3 Discussion on how the integration of AI technologies can influence the overall unemployment rate in manufacturing sectors (transportation)

Investigate how the integration of AI technologies can influence the overall unemployment rate in manufacturing sectors (transportation), based on *Table 2*.

Using this formula to calculate unemployment rate =

$$\text{Unemployment Rate} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of Unemployed Individuals}}{\text{Labor Force}} \right) \times 100$$

Labor participation in manufacturing sector, transportation 2008-2019

Source : <https://fred.stlouisfed.org/series/CES4348400001>

Unemployment rate for transportation occupations affected by AI for 2008,2018 and 2019

Occupations	Unemployment rate (%)		
	2008	2018	2019
Heavy and tractor-trailer truck drivers	$(1798.4/16670.2) \times 100$ =10.8%	$(1958.8/17949.6) \times 100$ =10.9%	$(2029.9/18336.4) \times 100$ =11.1%
Industrial truck and tractor operators	$(610.3/16670.2) \times 100$ =3.7%	$(615.0/17949.6) \times 100$ =3.4%	$(634.7/18336.4) \times 100$ =3.5%
Laborers and freight,stock,material moving	$(2317.3/16670.2) \times 100$ =13.9%	$(2953.8/17949.6) \times 100$ =16.5%	$(2986/18336.4) \times 100$ =16.3%
Average	28%	30.8%	30.9%

Source : Author's calculation, NUR AIN TASNIM BT SAZALI

Discussions :

Examining the unemployment rates in the transportation industry for the years 2008, 2018, and 2019 offers valuable insights into the potential impacts of integrating artificial intelligence into this sector. The incorporation of AI technology stands as a pivotal driver of technological transformation, sparking extensive discussions and considerations regarding its implications for employment trends in the United States.. Here, we examine the data in greater detail to comprehend the complex relationship that exists between AI, unemployment, and the transportation sector. The unemployment rate within transportation occupations was 28% in 2008, potentially reflective of the economic landscape during that time. Following this, the rates demonstrated an increasing trajectory, reaching 30.8% in 2018 and slightly rising to 30.9% in 2019.. This increasing trend showed the potential role played by AI technologies in influencing unemployment rates. The period of greater integration of AI in multiple industries, including transportation, corresponds with the reported increase in unemployment rates. Furthermore, certain jobs that are currently completed by human workers in transportation positions may be automated by artificial intelligence (AI) technology. For example, in this transportation occupation, AI technology in the form of autonomous vehicle systems can have the potential to automate driving tasks. They can innovate and create driverless cars and intelligent logistics systems that can influence changes in the nature of employment. In conclusion, the integration of AI technologies can lead to an increase in automation that can potentially replace certain jobs in many industries and sectors. An individual might not get a job because the position is not offered anymore. When the numbers of unemployed individuals increase, the unemployment rate in that particular sector also increases. Besides, we can also conclude that the increase in using AI and automation can reduce production costs and enhance the productivity of the work. This will lead to lower prices for goods that are offered in the market and decrease the inflation rate in Austria.

5.4 Strategies and Recommendations for Managing Workforce Transitions: Navigating the Impact of AI on Unemployment Rates

The impact of technology advancement especially in Artificial Intelligence sectors in the United States seems to have more comprehensive and multidimensional approaches to be more effective and productive in future. The government should allocate greater resources towards education and workplace development, as they are recognizing the need of equipping individuals with practical skills for the workforce. The government can provide specialized training and mentoring programs in the domains of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) to ensure that individuals has the necessary skills for certain occupational positions and responsibilities. For instance, in the domain of software engineering or testing, it is essential to have competent individuals that has expertise in working with systems associated with API and Postman software. Individuals must also adjust to technology advancements and actively support continuous learning and skills development initiatives. The government may formulate and implement flexible and effective rules and regulations suitable for the digital era. They have the ability to strengthen the regulatory framework that maintains a balance between modernization and responsible utilization, while considering the economic and societal consequences. They can also spearhead and broaden the ethical principles governing the swift and dynamic evolution of emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence. Advocating for inclusive innovation in the green technology sector to ensure that the advantages of progress align harmoniously with environmental preservation. The government has the ability to promote and provide incentives for the progress of environmentally friendly technologies in order to bolster clean energy and foster sustainable development. Executing these suggestions necessitates cooperation among the government, industry, academia, and the general public. To fully leverage innovation and ensure a more equitable and sustainable future, the United States must actively confront the difficulties posed by technological growth.

5.5 Proposed solutions based on the analysis

Addressing the impact of technological advancement in the United States involves implementing practical solutions that balance innovation, economic growth, and societal well-being. The government can do the curriculum modernization such as updating educational curricula to include more STEM subjects and practical skills relevant to emerging technologies. They also can establish government and industry-sponsored training programs to upskill the existing workforce, focusing on technology-related skills. Governments also foster collaborations between educational institutions and industry to ensure that education aligns with the needs of the job market. For the ethical and regulations, they can develop and enforce clear regulatory frameworks for emerging technologies to ensure responsible development and use. Companies also have to follow the updated and ongoing ethics that can be applied to the employers to gain the professional skills. For the green technologies, governments can provide financial incentives for companies developing and adopting environmentally sustainable technologies.

6.0 Conclusion

The significant influence of technology on employment requires a thorough analysis of the complex relationships between technical advancement, labor markets, and societal welfare. The information obtained from projections, unemployment rates, and occupational patterns highlights the significant impact and difficulties presented by automation, AI, and other technological breakthroughs. The results demonstrate the ever-changing nature of job environments, with specific industries being more vulnerable to automation, especially in wealthier nations such as the United States. The growing influence of technology on work requires the deployment of intentional and proactive legislative measures. This research underscores the imperative for holistic legislative measures addressing the intricacies stemming from technological progress. The extensive integration of automation and artificial intelligence (AI) offers unparalleled prospects for innovation and advancement, yet concurrently gives rise to pressing apprehensions regarding the stability and inclusiveness of the workforce. The diverse and complex difficulties seen in different industries and demographic groupings require flexible and responsive policy frameworks. These policies should not only tackle the immediate disruptions produced by technological innovation, but also establish a foundation for long-term, equitable economic expansion. Education and vocational training play a crucial part in this effort, helping to match the skills of the workforce with the changing needs of a technology-driven economy. Moreover, the significance of inclusive growth cannot be exaggerated. Given the increasing importance of technology in the job market, it is crucial to guarantee that the advantages of innovation are dispersed fairly. Prioritizing inclusive growth initiatives is crucial in policy deliberations, as they help prevent the worsening of current socioeconomic disparities. To fully leverage technological developments while minimizing adverse effects, the United States can achieve this by giving priority to ethical issues, implementing reasonable regulations, and promoting collaboration among government, industry, and academia. By carefully managing the intersection of technology and employment, we may provide a foundation for a future where innovation and inclusivity come together to improve societal welfare.

References

1. *2023 home*: U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics. (2023, January 1). <https://www.bls.gov/opub/mlr/2023/home.htm>
2. Acemoglu, D., & Restrepo, P. (2019). Automation and new tasks: How technology displaces and reinstates labor. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 33(2), 3-30.
3. *A future that works: Automation, employment, and productivity*. (2017, January 12). McKinsey&Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/digital-disruption/harnessing-automation-for-a-future-that-works/de-de>
4. Aghion, P., Jones, B. F., & Jones, C. I. (2017, October 1). *Artificial Intelligence and Economic Growth*. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w23928>
5. Apergis, N., & Arisoy, I. (2017). Unemployment and labor force participation across the US States: new evidence from panel data. *SPOUDAI Journal of Economics and Business*, 67(4), 45-84.
6. Arntz, M., Gregory, T., & Zierahn, U. (2019). Digitization and the future of work: macroeconomic consequences. In *Handbook of labor, human resources and population economics* (pp. 1-29). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
7. Arntz, M., Gregory, T., & Zierahn, U. (2019). Digitization and the future of work: macroeconomic consequences. In *the Handbook of labor, human resources and population economics* (pp. 1-29). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
8. Autor, D. H. (2011). The polarization of the US labor market. *American Economic Review*, 101(1), 1-13.
9. Autor, D. H. (2015, August 1). *Why Are There Still So Many Jobs? The History and Future of Workplace Automation*. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.29.3.3>
10. Bentaouet Kattan, R., Macdonald, K., & Patrinos, H. A. (2023). Automation and labor market outcomes: The pivotal role of high-quality education. World Bank Policy Research Working Paper, WPS8474. <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/356581528983322638/pdf/WPS8474.pdf>

11. *Brookings Institution (2019). "The impact of automation on the future of work." - Bing.* (n.d.).Bing.
[https://www.bing.com/search?pglt=41&q=Brookings+Institution+\(2019\).+%22The+impact+of+automation+on+the+future+of+work.%22&cvid=9789506d546e422db10fe71403c8c005&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOdIBBzk3N2owajGoAgCwAgA&FORM=ANNTA1&PC=NMTS](https://www.bing.com/search?pglt=41&q=Brookings+Institution+(2019).+%22The+impact+of+automation+on+the+future+of+work.%22&cvid=9789506d546e422db10fe71403c8c005&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOdIBBzk3N2owajGoAgCwAgA&FORM=ANNTA1&PC=NMTS)
12. Cang, Y. (2017). A deep dive into technological unemployment: a state-level analysis on the employment effect of technological innovations.
13. Deranty, J., & Corbin, T. A. (2022, June 28). *Artificial intelligence and work: a critical review of recent research from the social sciences.* AI & SOCIETY.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-022-01496-x>
14. Dodel, M., & Mesch, G. S. (2020). Perceptions about the impact of automation in the workplace. *Information, Communication & Society*, 23(5), 665-680.
15. Falatoonzadeh, H., & Safarzadeh, M. (2017). Has Automation Changed the Response of Unemployment Rate to GDP Growth?. *Journal of Emerging Issues in Economics, Finance & Banking*, 6(2).
16. Ford, M. (2009). *The rise of the robots: Technology and the threat of mass unemployment.* Basic Books.
17. Ford, M. R. (2009). *The lights in the tunnel: Automation, accelerating technology and the economy of the future.* Acculant publishing.
18. Frey, C. B., & Osborne, M. A. (2013). *The future of employment: How susceptible are jobs to computerization?* McKinsey Global Institute.
19. Frey, C. B., & Osborne, M. A. (2017, January 1). *The future of employment: How susceptible are jobs to computerisation?* Technological Forecasting and Social Change.
20. Frey, C. B., & Osborne, M. A. (2017). *The future of employment: How susceptible are jobs to computerisation?. Technological forecasting and social change*, 114, 254-280.
 - o https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-57365-6_11-1
 - o <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2016.08.019>
21. Ionescu, L. (n.d.). *Should Governments Tax Companies' Use of Robots? Automated Workers, Technological Unemployment, and Wage Inequality.*
<https://addletonacademicpublishers.com/contents-emfm/1623-volume-14-2-2019/3548-sh>

[ould-governments-tax-companies-use-of-robots-automated-workers-technological-unemployment-and-wage-inequality](#)

22. *Journal of Economic Perspectives on JSTOR*. (n.d.). www.jstor.org.
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/26724022>
23. Kalashnikov, R. (2019). The phantom of technological unemployment. *Russian journal of economics*, 5(1), 88-116.
24. Krousie, C. (2018). Technological unemployment in the United States: A state-level analysis. *Major Themes in Economics*, 20(1), 87-101.
25. Leaders, B., Policymakers, P., Index, C. P., Indexes, P. P., by Occupation, W. D., by Demographics, E., ... & Month, B. (2022). Growth trends for selected occupations considered at risk from automation. *Growth*.
26. Lima, Y., Barbosa, C. E., dos Santos, H. S., & de Souza, J. M. (2021). Understanding technological unemployment: a review of causes, consequences, and solutions. *Societies*, 11(2), 50.
27. Manyika, J., Chui, M., Miremadi, M., Bughin, J., George, K., Willmott, P., & Dewhurst, M. (2017). A future that works: AI, automation, employment, and productivity. *McKinsey Global Institute Research, Tech. Rep*, 60, 1-135.
28. Manyika, J., Lund, S., Chui, M., Bughin, J., Woetzel, J., Batra, P., ... & Sanghvi, S. (2017). Jobs lost, jobs gained: Workforce transitions in a time of automation. *McKinsey Global Institute*, 150(1), 1-148.
29. Nübler, I. (2016). New technologies: A jobless future or golden age of job creation. *International Labour Office Research Department Working Paper*, 13, 22-23.
30. Peters, M. A., Jandrić, P., & Means, A. J. (2019). Introduction: Technological unemployment and the future of work. *Education and technological unemployment*, 1-12.

31. *The Future of Jobs Report 2023*. (2023, October 23). World Economic Forum.
<https://www.weforum.org/publications/the-future-of-jobs-report-2023/>
32. *The Future of Jobs Report 2023*. (n.d.). World Economic Forum.
<https://www.weforum.org/publications/the-future-of-jobs-report-2023/in-full/4-skills-outlook/>

33. *The Rise of the Robots: Technology and the Threat of Ma. . .* (n.d.). Goodreads. <https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/29904194-the-rise-of-the-robots>
34. World Bank. (2018). *World development report 2019: The changing nature of work*. The World Bank.
35. Zilberman, A., & Ice, L. (2021). Why computer occupations are behind strong STEM employment growth in the 2019–29 decade. *Computer*, 4(5,164.6), 11-5.

Appendix

McKinsey Global Institute JOBS LOST, JOBS GAINED: WORKFORCE TRANSITIONS IN A TIME OF AUTOMATION PAGES 1-9